
Clinical Study Protocol: Appendix H

Study Code 4522US/0011

Version No. 2.0

Appendix Date 15 January, 2003

Appendix H

Management of Increased Creatine Kinase (CK)

MANAGEMENT OF INCREASED CREATINE KINASE (CK)

- Subjects should be advised to promptly report unexplained muscle pain or weakness
- Myopathy is defined as muscle aches or weakness in conjunction with increases in CK > 10 x ULN, should be recorded as an adverse event
- Should markedly elevated CK levels occur or myopathy diagnosed or suspected, trial therapy should be discontinued
- Trial therapy should be temporarily withheld or discontinued in any subject with an acute, serious condition suggestive of myopathy, or if a condition predisposing to the development of renal failure secondary to rhabdomyolysis (eg. Sepsis, hypotension, major surgery, trauma, severe metabolic, endocrine or electrolyte disorders, or uncontrolled seizures) is present

Clinical Study Protocol: Appendix I

Study Code 4522US/0011

Version No. 2.0

Appendix Date 15 January, 2003

Appendix I
Disallowed Concomitant Medications

DISALLOWED CONCOMITANT MEDICATIONS

CLASS OF DRUG	GENERIC NAME
Antiobesity	orlistat
Lipid regulation	niacin/nicotinic acid (includes vitamins / supplements with >50 mg niacin/nicotinic acid) probucol clofibrate cholestyramine except as specified in the protocol colestipol hydrochloride except as specified in the protocol fenofibrate gemfibrozil atorvastatin lovastatin pravastatin simvastatin fluvastatin ezetimibe except as specified in the protocol fish oils (any dose) lipid lowering dietary supplements lipid lowering food additives
Immunosuppressants	lymphocyte immune globulin rho(d) immune globulin azathioprine sodium muromonab-CD3 cyclosporin rapamycin tacrolimus mycophenolate mofetil
Chronic use of steroids	prednisone, prednisolone, dexamethasone, hydrocortisone
Viral suppressants	protease inhibitors
Oral Hormone Replacement Therapy	estrogens progestins

Clinical Study Protocol Amendment

Amendment No. 02
Study Code 4522US/0011
Date 29 April, 2003

JUPITER

A Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled, Multicenter, Phase III Study of Rosuvastatin (Crestor[®]) 20 mg in the Primary Prevention of Cardiovascular Events Among Subjects with Low Levels of LDL-Cholesterol and Elevated Levels of C-Reactive Protein

Sponsor:

AstraZeneca Pharmaceuticals LP, 1800 Concord Pike, Wilmington, DE 19850-5437.

Centres affected by the amendment:

All centers.

The protocol for the study is to be amended as follows:

Protocol Synopsis, Study center(s) and number of subjects planned

Previous text:

This study will be conducted in approximately 15,000 male and female subjects **recruited from the United States (approximately 500 centers)**. It is planned to recruit approximately 30 subjects per center.

Revised text:

This study will be conducted in approximately 15,000 male and female subjects **recruited from the United States (approximately 400 centers) and from Canada (approximately 100 centers)**. It is planned to recruit approximately 30 subjects per center.

Protocol Synopsis, Comparator, dosage and mode of administration

Previous text:

No comparator will be used.

Revised text:

No **active** comparator will be used.

Section 3.1 Overall study design and flow chart, paragraph 2

Previous text:

Approximately 15,000 subjects, men 55 years or older and women 65 years or older, will be randomized and followed for a period of approximately 3.5 years to accrue the 520 clinical endpoints upon which the study is powered (see Section 6.1). Subjects will be **recruited from the United States (approximately 500 centers)**; each center will recruit approximately 30 subjects.

Revised text:

Approximately 15,000 subjects, men 55 years or older and women 65 years or older, will be randomized and followed for a period of approximately 3.5 years to accrue the 520 clinical endpoints upon which the study is powered (see Section 6.1). Subjects will be **recruited from the United States (approximately 400 centers) and from Canada (approximately 100 centers)**; each center will recruit approximately 30 subjects.

Section 3.1 Overall study design and flow chart, paragraph 4

Previous text:

At Week 13, all randomized study subjects will return for an initial Safety Visit; at this time a safety blood sample will be obtained. Throughout the study, subjects will be seen for study assessments at 6-month intervals (see Table 4) until they reach either the study endpoint or study completion.

Revised text:

At 3 months, all randomized study subjects will return for an initial Safety Visit; at this time a safety blood sample will be obtained. Throughout the study, subjects will be seen for study assessments at 6-month intervals (see Table 4) until they reach either the study endpoint or study completion.

Section 3.1 Overall study design and flow chart, paragraph 7

Previous text:

For subjects with ≥ 2 CHD risk factors, whose LDL levels rise to ≥ 130 mg/dL during the study, the following procedure will be followed, in accordance with NCEP ATP III guidelines.

- a) The site will be notified by the central lab of the rise
- b) An additional visit should be scheduled to repeat fasting lipid profile in 6 weeks
- c) If the repeat LDL-C level is < 130 mg/dL, no changes are instituted and subject should return for the next scheduled visit per protocol
- d) If the repeat LDL-C level is ≥ 130 mg/dL, the Framingham risk is calculated by the central lab and the subject should be initiated on Therapeutic Lifestyle Changes (TLC), as defined by NCEP ATP III. In addition, subjects whose 10-year risk is $\geq 10\%$, are asked to return for an additional fasting lipid profile in 3 months; subjects whose 10-year risk is $< 10\%$ are asked to return for the next scheduled visit per protocol
- e) *After 3 months of TLC* the site is notified of subjects whose 10-year risk is $> 10\%$ and LDL-C level is ≥ 130 mg/dL
- f) *These subjects* should be evaluated by the investigator for the appropriateness of initiation of lipid-lowering drug therapy. If this is deemed necessary, it is recommended that a bile-acid sequestrant (eg. colestipol) or cholesterol absorption inhibitors (ezetimibe) are considered as first-line therapy. However, if in the opinion of the investigator, an HMG CoA reductase inhibitor is indicated, the subject should discontinue the blinded study medication before treatment initiation
- g) *If blinded medication is discontinued, the subject should return for all subsequent follow-up visits.*

Revised text:

For subjects with ≥ 2 CHD risk factors, whose LDL levels rise to ≥ 130 mg/dL (**3.36 mmol/L**)

during the study, the following procedure will be followed, in accordance with NCEP ATP III guidelines.

- a) The site will be notified by the central lab of the rise.
- b) An additional visit should be scheduled to repeat fasting lipid profile in 6 weeks.
- c) If the repeat LDL-C level is <130 mg/dL (**3.36 mmol/L**), no changes are instituted and subject should return for the next scheduled visit per protocol.
- d) If the repeat LDL-C level is ≥ 130 mg/dL (**3.36 mmol/L**), the Framingham risk is calculated by the central lab and the subject should be initiated on Therapeutic Lifestyle Changes (TLC), as defined by NCEP ATP III. In addition, subjects whose 10-year risk is $\geq 10\%$, are asked to return for an additional fasting lipid profile in 3 months; subjects whose 10-year risk is $<10\%$ are asked to return for the next scheduled visit per protocol.
- e) *After 3 months of TLC* the site is notified of subjects whose 10-year risk is $>10\%$ and LDL-C level is ≥ 130 mg/dL (**3.36 mmol/L**).
- f) *These subjects* should be evaluated by the investigator for the appropriateness of initiation of lipid-lowering drug therapy. If this is deemed necessary, it is recommended that a bile-acid sequestrant (eg. colestipol) or cholesterol absorption inhibitors (eg. ezetimibe) are considered as first-line therapy. However, if in the opinion of the investigator, an HMG CoA reductase inhibitor is indicated, the subject should discontinue the blinded study medication before treatment initiation.
- g) *If blinded medication is discontinued, the subject should return for all subsequent follow-up visits.*

Section 3.1 Overall study design and flow chart

Previous text:

Screening Visit 2 (Week -4)

- Inclusion/exclusion eligibility confirmed
- Fasting blood sample taken for analysis of CRP, ALT, CK, Apolipoprotein (Apo) A-1 and Apo B-100, creatinine, TSH, fasting serum glucose (FSG), HbA_{1c} and complete blood count (CBC)
- Urinalysis

NOTE: Plasma and buffy coat samples obtained at Visit 2, in addition to being used for cholesterol, CRP, and safety evaluations, will also be stored for future use in genomic and proteomic analyses relating to lipid metabolism, inflammatory function, and statin therapy. Samples for genetic analyses will be retained only for those subjects who have signed the addendum to the informed consent at Visit 1. To ensure participant confidentiality, these additional study samples will be coded with separate participant identifiers during the course of the study and will be rendered fully anonymous after the study has been completed.

- Physical exam performed
- Waist circumference taken
- Screening medical history obtained concerning cardiovascular risk factors, family history of premature coronary disease, and co-morbid conditions
- Prior/current medications recorded
- Run-in study medication dispensed to subject
- Subjects who do not meet the entry criteria should be considered screen failures and a Screen Fail Case Report Form (CRF) should be completed

Revised text:

Screening Visit 2 (Week -4)

- Inclusion/exclusion eligibility confirmed
- Fasting blood sample taken for analysis of CRP, ALT, CK, Apolipoprotein (Apo) A-1 and Apo B-100, creatinine, TSH, fasting serum glucose (FSG), HbA_{1c} and complete blood count (CBC)

NOTE: Plasma and buffy coat samples obtained at Visit 2, in addition to being used for CRP and safety evaluations, will also be stored for future use in genomic and proteomic analyses relating to lipid metabolism, inflammatory function, and statin therapy. Samples for genetic analyses will be retained only for those subjects who have signed the addendum to the informed consent at Visit 1. To ensure participant confidentiality, these additional study samples will be coded with separate participant identifiers during the course of the study and will be rendered fully anonymous after the study has been completed.

- Urinalysis
- Physical exam performed
- Waist circumference taken

- Screening medical history obtained concerning cardiovascular risk factors, family history of premature coronary disease, and co-morbid conditions
- **Adverse experiences assessed**
- **Endpoint and diabetes mellitus (DM) assessed**
- Prior/current medications recorded
- Run-in study medication dispensed to subject
- Subjects who do not meet the entry criteria should be considered screen failures and a Screen Fail Case Report Form (CRF) should be completed

Previous text:

Visit 6 (12-Month Visit)

- Study medication compliance checked
- Endpoint and DM assessed
- Adverse experiences assessed
- Concomitant medications recorded
- Fasting blood samples taken for analysis of TC, LDL-C, HDL-C, TG, Apo A-1 and Apo B-100, CRP, and ALT
- Urinalysis
- Study medication dispensed

Revised text:

Visit 6 (12-Month Visit)

- Study medication compliance checked
- Endpoint and DM assessed
- Adverse experiences assessed
- Concomitant medications recorded

- Fasting blood samples taken for analysis of TC, LDL-C, HDL-C, TG, Apo A-1 and Apo B-100, CRP, ALT, and plasma reserve
- Urinalysis
- Study medication dispensed

Table 4 Study plan

Additional checks added at Visit 2 to indicate Endpoint and DM Assessment and Adverse Event Assessment.

Section 3.3.3 Exclusion criteria

Additional exclusion criterion added after existing criterion #7:

8. Serum creatinine >2.0 mg/dL (177 umol/L) at Screening Visit 2

Section 3.3.4.3 Incorrectly enrolled or randomized subjects, paragraph 1

Previous text:

Incorrectly **enrolled** subjects will continue to receive study treatment and assessments if, in the opinion of the investigator and/or study team physician, this is not considered to involve any risk or discomfort to the subject. There should be no attempt to switch treatment or change randomization numbers.

Revised text:

Incorrectly **randomized** subjects will continue to receive study treatment and assessments if, in the opinion of the investigator and/or study team physician, this is not considered to involve any risk or discomfort to the subject. There should be no attempt to switch treatment or change randomization numbers.

Section 3.3.4.5 Procedures for lost-to-follow-up, paragraph 3

Previous text:

For subjects who miss a scheduled study visit, there should be 3 separate attempts of contacting the subject. All attempts at trying to contact study participants should be well documented by the investigative site including search of National Death Index.

Revised text:

For subjects who miss a scheduled study visit, there should be **at least** 3 separate attempts of contacting the subject. All attempts at trying to contact study participants should be well documented by the investigative site including search of National Death Index.

Section 3.4.1.2 Labeling

Previous text:

All bottles will be labeled with at least a study reference number, a bottle reference number, administrative instructions, and storage conditions. This label will have a detachable tear-off portion, which will be attached to the appropriate case report form (CRF) at the time of dispensing. The label will also contain a space for subject number, subject initials, visit number and the date dispensed.

Revised text:

All bottles will be labeled with at least a study reference number, a bottle reference number, administrative instructions, and storage conditions. This label will have a detachable tear-off portion, which will be attached to the appropriate case report form (CRF) at the time of dispensing. The label will also contain a space for subject number, subject initials (**US sites only**), visit number, **Investigator name (Canadian sites only)** and the date dispensed.

Section 3.4.1.3 Storage, paragraph 2

Previous text:

All study drugs are to be stored in their original containers in a lockable storage facility until dispensed to the study subjects. **Study medications should not be frozen but should be protected from light and moisture at temperatures between 68 and 77°F (20 and 25°C).**

Revised text:

All study drugs are to be stored in their original containers in a lockable storage facility until dispensed to the study subjects. **Study medications should be protected from light and moisture.**

US sites: Store between 68 and 77°F (20 and 25°C).

Canadian sites: Store between 15-25°C.

Section 3.4.3 Method of assigning subjects to treatment groups, paragraph 3

Previous text:

The study medication will be blinded by providing rosuvastatin and placebo tablets, which are indistinguishable in appearance. Subject numbers will be allocated strictly sequentially as subjects are determined to be eligible for enrollment/randomization. Once a number has been assigned, no attempt should be made to use that number again if, for example, a subject is withdrawn from the study. No subject should be randomized into the study more than once.

Revised text:

The study medication will be blinded by providing rosuvastatin and placebo tablets, which are indistinguishable in appearance. **Subject eligibility will be established before treatment randomization.** Subject numbers will be allocated strictly sequentially as subjects are **determined to be eligible to be screened for the study.** Once a number has been assigned, no attempt should be made to use that number again if, for example, a subject is withdrawn from the study. No subject should be randomized into the study more than once.

Section 3.4.3.1 Interactive Voice Response System (IVRS)

Previous text:

IVRS will be used for subject registration, study medication assignment, allocation of subject numbers as subjects are randomized, and emergency code breaks. The IVRS technology will be managed and maintained by Perceptive Informatics, Inc. The system is accessible by telephone 24 hours a day, 7 days a week via a toll free number. The IVRS manual, which has full details of the operation and use of the IVRS, will be provided to each site. Training on the use of IVRS will also be given.

Revised text:

IVRS will be used for subject registration **starting at Visit 2**, study medication assignment, allocation of subject numbers as subjects are randomized, and emergency code breaks. The IVRS technology will be managed and maintained by Perceptive Informatics, Inc. The system is accessible by telephone 24 hours a day, 7 days a week via a toll free number. The IVRS manual, which has full details of the operation and use of the IVRS, will be provided to each site. Training on the use of IVRS will also be given.

Section 3.4.6 Treatment compliance, paragraph 2

Previous text:

Any subject taking < 80% of the prescribed study medication during the run-in phase will be considered non-compliant. Compliance will be checked at each visit after enrollment to the treatment period.

Revised text:

Any subject taking $\leq$ 80% of the prescribed study medication during the run-in phase will be considered non-compliant. Compliance will be checked at each visit after enrollment to the treatment period.

Section 4.4.2.1 Definitions, Other significant adverse event

Previous text:

An AstraZeneca **expert** will identify OAEs during the evaluation of safety data for the Clinical Study Report (CSR). Significant adverse events of particular clinical importance, other than SAEs and those AEs leading to discontinuation of the subject from study treatment, will be classified as OAEs. Examples of these are marked hematological and other laboratory abnormalities, and certain events that lead to intervention (other than those already classified as serious), dose reduction or significant additional treatment. For each OAE, a narrative will be written and included in the CSR.

Revised text:

An AstraZeneca **Drug Safety Physician and if applicable the Clinical Study Team Physician** will identify OAEs during the evaluation of safety data for the Clinical Study Report (CSR). Significant adverse events of particular clinical importance, other than SAEs and those AEs leading to discontinuation of the subject from study treatment, will be classified as OAEs. Examples of these are marked hematological and other laboratory abnormalities, and certain events that lead to intervention (other than those already classified as serious), dose reduction or significant additional treatment. For each OAE, a narrative will be written and included in the CSR.

Section 4.4.2.2 Recording of adverse events, paragraph 1

Previous text:

Adverse events will be identified by means of a standard question such as, “Have you had any health problems since the previous visit?” The question will be asked of each subject at all study visits following randomization. All adverse events must be recorded in the CRF provided.

Revised text:

Adverse events will be identified by means of a standard question such as, “Have you had any health problems since the previous visit?” **The question will be asked of each subject at all study visits once Informed Consent has been signed by the subject.** All adverse events must be recorded in the CRF provided.

Section 4.4.2.2 Recording of adverse events, last paragraph

Previous text:

Subjects will be followed for 30 days after the final dose of study medication and/or discharge from the study in case they should develop new serious adverse events. Any adverse events or serious adverse events which are unresolved when the subject completes or discontinues the study will be followed until resolution or until they return to baseline, as decided by the investigator.

Revised text:

Subjects will be followed for 30 days after final visit. Any adverse events or serious adverse events which are unresolved when the subject completes or discontinues the study will be followed until resolution or until they return to baseline, as decided by the investigator.

Section 4.4.2.3 Reporting of serious adverse events, paragraph 5

Previous text:

Serious adverse event data will be collected during the study period and within 30 days after **the last dose of study medication.**

Revised text:

Serious adverse event data will be collected during the study period and within 30 days after **the final visit.**

Section 4.4.3.1 Methods of assessment, paragraph 9

Previous text:

A fasting lipid profile and CRP measurement will also be done at Visits 6, 8, 10, and Visit F. In addition, Apo A-1 and Apo B-100 will be assessed at Visits 2, 6, and Visit F.

Revised text:

A fasting lipid profile and CRP measurement will also be done at Visits 6, 8, 10, and Visit F. **CRP will also be measured at Visits 2 and 4.** In addition, Apo A-1 and Apo B-100 will be assessed at Visits 2, 6, and Visit F.

Section 4.4.3.1 Methods of assessment

Additional paragraph added after existing paragraph 11

To ensure study integrity, CRP and Lipid Panel results will remain blinded throughout the duration of the study.

Section 7.1 Monitoring, paragraph 1, 2nd bullet

Previous text:

Before the study begins, a representative of AstraZeneca will visit the investigational site to

- determine the adequacy of the facilities
- discuss with the investigator(s) (and other personnel involved with the study) their responsibilities with regard to protocol adherence, and the responsibilities of AstraZeneca or its representatives.

Revised text:

Before the study begins, a representative of AstraZeneca will visit the investigational site to

- determine the adequacy of the facilities
- discuss with the investigator(s) (and other personnel involved with the study) their responsibilities with regard to protocol adherence, and the responsibilities of AstraZeneca or its representatives. **This will be documented in a Clinical Study Agreement between AstraZeneca and the investigator.**

Section 8.2 Ethical conduct of the study

Previous text:

The study will be performed in accordance with the ethical principles in the Declaration of Helsinki (see Appendix C), **GCP**, and applicable regulatory requirements.

Revised text:

The study will be performed in accordance with the ethical principles in the Declaration of Helsinki (see Appendix C), **ICH/GCP**, and applicable regulatory requirements.

Section 8.3 Subject information and consent, paragraph 4

Previous text:

A sample Written Informed Consent Form is attached (Appendix B). If modifications are made according to local requirements, the new version has to be approved by AstraZeneca.

Revised text:

A sample Written Informed Consent Form will be provided under separate cover. If modifications are made according to local requirements, the new version has to be approved by AstraZeneca.

Section 8.4 Subject data protection

Added the following text before the current paragraph:

AstraZeneca recognizes the importance of protecting the privacy of patient (subject) data. Therefore, for study sites within the US or in studies where foreign subjects' protected health information (subject data) will come into the US through a covered entity (eg, Central Lab/Reader), the Informed Consent Form will incorporate, or be accompanied by, a separate document incorporating HIPAA-compliant wording by which subjects authorize the use and disclosure of their Protected Health Information by the Investigator and by those persons who need that information for the purposes of the study.

Appendix B, Sample Written Informed Consent Form

The Sample Informed Consent Form has been removed from Appendix B and will be provided under separate cover.

Appendix I, Disallowed Concomitant Medications

Colesevelam hydrochloride has been added to the list of Disallowed Concomitant Medications.

Reasons for making the amendment:

- Addition of Canadian participation in the study
- Clarification of study procedures

Signed agreement to the amendment:

I agree to the terms of this protocol amendment.

Study Code: 4522US/0011

.....
Date
(day, month, year)

.....
AstraZeneca signatory
[REDACTED]
Senior Medical Director
Astra Zeneca LP
1800 Concord Pike
Wilmington, DE 19850

C

Protocol Amendment No. 02
Study code 4522US/0011

I agree to the terms of this protocol amendment.

Study Code: 4522US/0011

Centre No.: N/A

.....
Date
(day, month, year)

.....
Primary investigator
Paul M Ridker, MD, MPH, FACC
Director, Center of Cardiovascular Disease Prevention
Brigham and Women's Hospital
Harvard Medical School
900 Commonwealth Avenue East
Boston, MA 02215

Protocol Amendment No. 02
Study code 4522US/0011

I agree to the terms of this protocol amendment.

Study Code: 4522US/0011

Centre No.: <<>>

.....
Date
(day, month, year)

.....
Principal investigator
<< Name and Address >>

Clinical Study Protocol Amendment

Amendment Number	03
Drug Substance	Rosuvastatin
Study Code	4522US/0011
Date	21 October 2004

JUPITER

Justification for the Use of statins in Primary prevention: an Intervention Trial Evaluating Rosuvastatin

A Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled, Multicenter, Phase III Study of Rosuvastatin (CRESTOR®) 20 mg in the Primary Prevention of Cardiovascular Events Among Subjects with Low Levels of LDL-Cholesterol and Elevated Levels of C-Reactive Protein

Sponsor:

AstraZeneca Pharmaceuticals LP, 1800 Concord Pike, Wilmington, DE 19850-5437.

Centers affected by the Amendment:

All Centers.

Reason for Amendment:

Expanding recruitment outside of the United States and Canada; clarification regarding subject follow-up

Persons who initiated the Amendment:

AstraZeneca Clinical Study Team

The protocol for the study is to be amended as follows:

Section of protocol affected:

Protocol Synopsis, Study Centers and Number of Subjects Planned

Previous text:

This study will be conducted in approximately 15,000 male and female subjects **recruited from the United States (up to 800 centers) and from Canada (up to 250 centers).**

Revised Text:

This study will be conducted in approximately 15,000 male and female **randomised** subjects **potentially recruited from the following areas:**

United States – approximately 8,000 subjects, approximately 800 centers

Canada - approximately 2,000 subjects, approximately 150 centers

Belgium – approximately 500 subjects, approximately 50 centers

Israel – approximately 200 subjects, approximately 15 centers

Estonia – approximately 100 subjects, approximately 15 centers

Latin America – approximately 3,000 subjects, approximately 200 centers

Denmark – approximately 1,000 subjects, approximately 100 centers

Germany – approximately 1,000 subjects, approximately 100 centers

Italy – approximately 2,000 subjects, approximately 200 centers

Netherlands – approximately 3,000 subjects, approximately 20 centers

Norway – approximately 400 subjects, approximately 40 centers

United Kingdom – approximately 5,000 subjects, approximately 200 centers

Lebanon – approximately 500 subjects, approximately 50 centers

Switzerland – approximately 300 subjects, approximately 30 centers

Section of protocol affected:

Protocol Synopsis, Study Period

Previous text:

Study period		Phase of development
Estimated date of first subject enrolled	February 2003	III

Estimated date of last subject completed	December 2007	
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Revised Text:

Study period		Phase of development
Estimated date of first subject enrolled	February 2003	III
Estimated date of last subject completed	October 2008	

Section of protocol affected:

3.1 Overall study design and flow chart

Previous text:

None

Revised Text:

This Clinical Study Protocol has been subjected to a peer review according to AstraZeneca standard procedures.

Section of protocol affected:

3.1 Overall study design and flow chart, Paragraph 2

Previous text:

Subjects will be recruited from the United States (up to 800 centers) and from Canada (up to 250 centers).

Revised Text:

Subjects will potentially be recruited from the following areas:

United States – approximately 8,000 subjects, approximately 800 centers

Canada - approximately 2,000 subjects, approximately 150 centers

Belgium – approximately 500 subjects, approximately 50 centers

Israel – approximately 200 subjects, approximately 15 centers

Estonia – approximately 100 subjects, approximately 15 centers

Latin America – approximately 3,000 subjects, approximately 200 centers

Denmark – approximately 1,000 subjects, approximately 100 centers

Germany – approximately 1,000 subjects, approximately 100 centers

Italy – approximately 2,000 subjects, approximately 200 centers

Netherlands – approximately 3,000 subjects, approximately 20 centers

Norway – approximately 400 subjects, approximately 40 centers

United Kingdom – approximately 5,000 subjects, approximately 200 centers

Lebanon – approximately 500 subjects, approximately 50 centers

Switzerland – approximately 300 subjects, approximately 30 centers

Section of protocol affected:

3.1 Overall study design and flow chart, Paragraph 4

Previous text:

At 3 months, all randomised study subjects will return for an initial Safety Visit; at this time a **safety** blood sample will be obtained. Throughout the study, subjects will be seen for study assessments at six-month intervals (see Table 4) **until they reach either the study endpoint or study completion**. Any randomised individual for whom alanine aminotransferase (ALT) levels are elevated to >3 x upper limit of normal (ULN) on 2 consecutive measurements will be asked to discontinue study medication. **However, such subjects will be continued to be followed for the study duration, as they have completed the randomisation process and thus are full participants in the study.**

Revised Text:

At 3 months, all randomised study subjects will return for an initial Safety Visit; at this time a blood sample will be obtained **for safety assessment**. Throughout the study, subjects will be seen for study assessments at six-month intervals (see Table 4) **for the duration of the study**. **All randomised subjects will be contacted by the site mid-way between their six-month visits regarding their study participation, and to confirm their address has not changed. All randomised subjects will have their final visit during the last 6 months of the study.** Any randomised individual for which alanine aminotransferase (ALT) levels are elevated up to >3 x upper limit normal (ULN) on 2 consecutive measurements **48 hours apart** will be asked to discontinue study medication. **As this is an endpoint study, it is essential that every randomised subject be followed for the duration of the study, including those that have been discontinued from study drug per investigator discretion or subject preference. Subjects that have been discontinued from study drug and are unable to attend an office visit may complete their scheduled visits via telephone contact to ensure that adverse events and endpoints are identified and recorded.**

Section of protocol affected:

3.1 Overall study design and flow chart, Paragraph 6

Previous text:

All randomised study subjects will be followed **over an estimated 3.5 year period** for the occurrence of a first ever acute cardiovascular event, defined as cardiovascular death, stroke, myocardial infarction, unstable angina, or arterial revascularization.

Revised Text:

All randomised study subjects will be followed **until study completion (an estimated 5 year period)** for the occurrence of a first ever acute cardiovascular event, defined as cardiovascular death, stroke, myocardial infarction, unstable angina, or arterial revascularization.

Section of protocol affected:

3.1 Overall study design and flow chart, Paragraph 7, section g

Previous text:

*If blinded medication is discontinued, the subject **should** return for all subsequent follow-up visits.*

Revised Text:

*If blinded medication is discontinued, the subject **will** return for all subsequent follow-up visits **until study completion**. **If the subject is not able to attend an office visit, telephone contacts may be made according to the subjects visit schedule to ensure that subsequent cardiovascular and adverse events are identified and recorded.***

Section of protocol affected:

3.1 Overall study design and flow chart, Paragraph 8

Previous text:

Once the study completes, all subjects will attend the clinic for their final visit (Visit F).

Revised Text:

During the final six months of the study, all subjects will attend the clinic for their final visit (Visit F). **For those randomised subjects in which study drug had previously been discontinued, a telephone contact may be made if the subject is unable to attend an office visit.**

Section of protocol affected:

3.1 Overall study design and flow chart, Screening Visit 1 (Week –6)

Previous text:

A screening informed consent will be obtained before any screening assessments are performed. If the subject is found to be eligible for the study, then the subject will be asked to sign the main study consent **before continuing the study.**

Revised Text:

If approved by the local regulatory authority, a screening informed consent will be obtained before any screening assessments are performed. If the subject is found to be eligible for the study, the subject will be asked to sign the main study consent form at Visit 2. If the screening informed consent is not approved by the local regulatory authority, the information contained in the screening informed consent and the main informed consent will be combined into one study informed consent form. If one main informed consent is used, the subject will sign at Visit 1 before any study related procedures are performed. (Please note that regardless of the type of study consent utilized, the consent for future genetic analysis addendum will not be obtained until Visit 2.)

Section of protocol affected:

3.1 Overall study design and flow chart, Screening Visit 2 (Week -4)

Previous text:

Full informed consent taken; this includes the addendum to the informed consent for those subjects who agree to have their samples stored for future genetic analysis.

Revised Text:

For those sites that are using a screening informed consent, full informed consent is obtained. This includes the addendum to the informed consent for those subjects who agree to have their samples stored for future genetic analysis. Consent to the genetic addendum is also obtained at this visit for those sites that are using only one consent.

Section of protocol affected:

3.3.4.1 Criteria for discontinuation

Previous text:

Subjects may be discontinued from study **treatment and assessments** at any time, at the discretion of the investigator of the investigator(s). Specific reasons for discontinuing a subject from **this** study are:

Revised Text:

Subjects may be discontinued from study **medication** at any time, at the discretion of the investigator(s). **It is essential that every randomised subject be followed for the duration of the study, including those that have been discontinued from study medication. Subjects who have been discontinued from study medication will complete their scheduled office visits, or may be contacted via phone by the site for the purpose of**

documenting endpoints. Specific reasons for discontinuing a subject from study **medication** are:

Section of protocol affected:

3.3.4.2 Voluntary discontinuation by a subject

Previous text:

Subjects who discontinue from the study should always be asked about the reason(s) for their discontinuation and about the presence of any adverse events. If possible, they should be seen and assessed by an investigator(s). Adverse events should be followed up and investigational products should be returned by the subject.

Revised Text:

Subjects who **request to** discontinue from the study should always be asked about the reason(s) for their discontinuation and about the presence of any **endpoints** or adverse events. If possible, they should be seen and assessed by an investigator(s). Adverse events should be followed up and investigational products should be returned by the subject. **At the time the subject expresses his/her desire to withdraw from the study, the study staff should ascertain from the subject whether the subject truly wishes to withdraw from the study entirely, or just discontinue study medication. Subjects who discontinue study medication have the option of being followed up by phone contact in accordance with their visit schedule if they are unable to attend office visits. Study medication may be restarted at any time unless contraindicated. As this is an endpoint study, it is essential that all randomised subjects be followed for the course of the study in order to document endpoints and vital status.**

Section of protocol affected:

3.3.4.3 Incorrectly enrolled or randomised subjects, Paragraph 2

Previous text:

In all other instances, incorrectly enrolled subjects will be discontinued from further study treatment and assessments if this will be associated with risk or discomfort for these subjects.

Revised Text:

If study medication is contraindicated, incorrectly randomised subjects will be discontinued from further study medication treatment, however, all follow-up visits and assessments must continue. A telephone contact may be made if the subject is unable to attend an office visit.

Section of protocol affected:

3.3.4.4 Procedures for discontinuation

Previous text:

For all discontinuations, the full assessments that are specified in Visit F should be carried out whenever possible.

Revised Text:

For discontinuation of study medication, the subjects will continue in the study according to their visit schedule. The reason for discontinuation of study medication must be documented on the CRF. Visit F will not be completed until the last 6 months of the study. For subjects that withdraw consent from the study, the full assessments that are specified in Visit F should be carried out to assure safety of the subject and to document any adverse events or endpoints at that time.

Section of protocol affected:

3.3.4.5 Procedures for lost to follow-up, Paragraph 3

Previous text:

For subjects who miss a scheduled study visit, there should be at least 3 separate attempts of contacting the subject. All attempts at trying to contact study participants should be well documented by the investigative site including search of the National Death index.

Revised Text:

For subjects who miss a scheduled study visit, at least 3 separate attempts must be made to contact the subject and re-schedule. Study medication can be restarted at any time during the study if deemed appropriate by the investigator(s). All attempts to contact subjects must be documented by the investigative site. Successful contacts must include verification of vital status as of the date of contact, and whether a study endpoint or adverse event has occurred. Any randomised subject for whom vital status has not been confirmed for greater than 1 year during the follow-up period will be considered lost-to-follow-up until contact has been re-established. Attempts to contact these subjects will be made by data base searches of the National Death Index or an external vendor to obtain vital status on all randomised subjects.

Section of protocol affected:

3.4 Treatments, Number 5

Previous text:

Any unused products are accounted for and returned to a designated facility or AstraZeneca for destruction.

Revised Text:

Any unused products are accounted for and either destroyed locally, or returned to a designated facility or to AstraZeneca for destruction.

Section of protocol affected:

3.4.1.2 Labeling, Paragraph 1

Previous text:

The label will **also contain a space for subject number, subject initials (US sites only), visit number, Investigator name (Canadian sites only) and the date dispensed.**

Revised Text:

The label will **at a minimum contain a space for subject number, visit number, and the date dispensed.**

Section of protocol affected:

3.4.1.3 Storage, Paragraph 2

Previous text:

All study drugs are to be stored in their original containers in a lockable storage facility until dispensed to the study subjects. **Study medications should be protected from light and moisture.**

US sites: Store between 68°F and 77°F (20°C and 25°C).

Canadian sites: Store between 15°C and 25°C.

Revised Text:

All study medications are to be stored in their original containers in a lockable storage facility until dispensed to the study subjects.

Section of protocol affected:

3.4.5 Pre-study, concomitant and post-study treatments, Paragraph 2

Previous text:

Disallowed drugs at both study entry and during follow-up include cyclosporin, tacrolimus, azathioprine, and other potent immunosuppressants, since the use of these agents may increase the risk of adverse events during rosuvastatin treatment.

Revised Text:

Disallowed drugs at both study entry and during follow-up include cyclosporin, tacrolimus, azathioprine, and other potent immunosuppressants, since the use of these agents may increase the risk of adverse events during rosuvastatin treatment. **After the subject has completed or discontinued the study, they will be treated according to the local medical practice.**

Section of protocol affected:

4.4.3.1 Methods of assessment, paragraph 4

Previous text:

Samples for evaluation from all investigational sites in this study will be delivered by courier within 24 hours of blood drawings to the central laboratory, Medical Research Laboratories International (MRLI).

Revised Text:

Shipment of samples to the central laboratory will be carried out according to the guidelines provided by the central laboratory. The samples are shipped the day of collection by express courier to ensure receipt by the central laboratory within the period of sample integrity. The appropriate documentation should accompany the samples.

Section of protocol affected:

7.5 Study Agreements, Paragraph 1

Previous text:

In the event of any inconsistency between this protocol and the study agreement, this study agreement shall prevail.

Revised Text:

In the event of any inconsistency between this protocol and the study agreement, the terms of the protocol shall prevail with respect to the conduct of the study and the treatment of subjects in connection there with; in all other respects, the terms of the study agreement shall prevail.

Section of protocol affected:

7.8 Study Timetable and termination, Paragraph 1

Previous text:

As such, recruitment is anticipated to end by December 2005 barring early termination by the IDMB.

Revised Text:

As such, recruitment is anticipated to end by December 2005 barring early termination by the IDMB. Database lock, which defines the end of the study, is anticipated in January 2009.

Section of protocol affected:

8.1 Ethics review, Paragraph 3

Previous text:

The Principal Investigator(s) must also provide the IEC or IRB with any reports of serious adverse events from the study site.

Revised Text:

The Principal Investigator(s) must also provide the IEC or IRB with any reports of serious adverse events from the study site. **AstraZeneca will provide IECs and Principal Investigators with safety updates/reports according to the requirements.**

Section of protocol affected:

9.1 AstraZeneca emergency contact procedure

Previous text:

In case of a medical emergency contact the PPD switchboard at 1-888-483-7729 and request to be put in contact with the assigned Medical Monitor for the JUPITER study.

Revised Text:

In case of a medical emergency, **US and Canadian sites should** contact the PPD switchboard at 1-888-483-7729 and request to be put in contact with the assigned Medical Monitor for the JUPITER study. **All other sites should refer to local emergency contact information found on page 2 of this document.**

Section of protocol affected:

9.3 Procedures in case of overdose

Previous text:

Clinical monitoring and general supportive measures should be given as appropriate.

Revised Text:

Clinical monitoring and general supportive measures should be given as appropriate.

An overdose with associated SAEs should be recorded as an SAE (diagnosis/symptoms) on the relevant AE forms in the CRF

An overdose with associated non-serious AEs should be recorded as an AE (diagnosis/symptoms) on the relevant AE forms in the CRF. The overdose should be reported on the separate AZ “Clinical Study Overdose Report Form”.

An overdose without associated symptoms should not be recorded as an AE in the CRF. The overdose should be reported on the separate AZ “Clinical Study Overdose Report Form”.

Section of protocol affected:

Appendix G Management of Elevated Liver Enzymes

Previous text:

Subjects who develop increased transaminases should be monitored until the abnormalities resolve according to the investigator's clinical judgement

Should an increase in ALT >3xULN occur on 2 consecutive measurements, with drawl of trial therapy is recommended

Revised Text:

ALT and other liver function tests should be measured at baseline and during the study as directed in the trial plan

Appropriate liver function tests should be measured at any other time if liver disease is suspected

A suitably experienced physician should be involved in interpreting the results and deciding appropriate management for the subject. The physician should be alerted to the occurrence of any ALT values >3xULN and significantly out-of-range values for other liver function tests. The following questioning and follow-up investigations should be considered:

Clarify the nature, duration and intensity of relevant symptoms

Review possible predisposing factors, such as: alcohol intake, viral illness (consider performing serology), concomitant medications including any recreational drug use, travel, blood transfusion, sexual behavior

Physical examination for jaundice and other signs of liver disease

Perform additional liver function tests, perhaps including ALT, AST, bilirubin, alkaline phosphatase, GGT, viral serology, prothombin time

Diagnostic imaging, such as ultrasound, CT, or MRI

Arrange to review the subject and repeat liver function tests after a suitable interval depending on the clinical picture (perhaps 4-10 days), or earlier if symptoms of liver disease appear or worsen

The Study Team Physician is available to give advice (see Emergency Contact details)

Statin-related ALT elevation is considered to be clinically significant if the ALT is increased to >3xULN on 2 consecutive occasions 48 hours apart. If this occurs without an obvious reversible precipitating factor, or if on clinical grounds, statin-induced liver disease is diagnosed or suspected, it is recommended that statin therapy should be discontinued. In these circumstances, and appropriate adverse event should be recorded, and the Study Team Physician must be informed

Study treatment must not be restarted without discussion with the study team physician

Section of protocol affected:

Appendix H Management of Increased Creatine Kinase (CK)

Previous text:

Subjects should be **advised** to promptly report unexplained muscle pain or weakness

Myopathy is defined as muscle aches or weakness in conjunction with increases in CK > 10xULN, and should be recorded as an adverse event

Should markedly elevated CK levels occur or myopathy diagnosed or suspected, trial therapy should be discontinued

Trial therapy should be temporarily withheld or discontinued in any subject with an acute, serious condition suggestive of myopathy, or if a condition predisposing to the development of renal failure secondary to rhabdomyolysis (e.g. Sepsis, hypotension, major surgery, trauma, severe metabolic, endocrine or electrolyte disorders, or uncontrolled seizures) is present

Revised Text:

Throughout the study, subjects should be **instructed** to promptly report any unexplained muscle pain or weakness, **particularly if associated with malaise or fever. If this occurs, creatine kinase (CK) should be measured as soon as possible.**

Also, if CK is found to be elevated > 5xULN on routine testing, the subject should be questioned about muscle symptoms

A study site physician should be alerted to the occurrence of unexplained muscle symptoms and any CK values > 5xULN, and must take immediate action if CK >10xULN

A suitably experienced physician should be involved in deciding appropriate management for the subject, taking account of any local guidelines

The following questioning and follow-up investigations should be considered:

Clarify the nature, duration and intensity of any muscle symptoms

Review possible predisposing factors, such as: unaccustomed exercise (including decorating, gardening etc), heavy alcohol intake, viral illness (consider performing serology), concomitant medications and consider diagnosis of other conditions which can cause myopathy

Physical examination for muscle tenderness, weakness and rash

Measure CK again within a few days

Measure serum creatinine

Urinalysis (including myoglobin and sediment)

Arrange to review the subject again in 4 to 10 days, or earlier if symptoms of myopathy appear or worsen, or if the urine becomes very dark

The Study Team Physician is available to give advice (see Emergency Contact details)

Myopathy is defined as muscle aches or weakness in association with CK increased to > 10xULN. If myopathy occurs without an obvious reversible precipitating factor, or if on clinical grounds, statin-induced myopathy is diagnosed or suspected, statin therapy should be discontinued. Myopathy should always be recorded as an adverse event, and the Study Team Physician must be informed.

Study treatment should not be restarted without discussion with the Study Team Physician